

THE ANCIENT EDUCATIONAL AND IDEOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE ORGANIZATION OF MUSIC CLUBS IN GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the opinions of Eastern thinkers about the importance of education from artistic aesthetic values, instilling the best human qualities into the minds of students and young people through music and bringing them to adulthood in a healthy way.

Keywords: music, culture, art, idea, creativity, aesthetic, education, tool, school, interest.

Аннотация: Мазкур мақолада шарқ мутафаккирларининг бадий эстетик қадриятлардан тарбиянинг муҳим аҳамияти, ўқувчи-ёшларнинг онгига мусиқа орқали энг яхши инсоний фазилатларини сингдириш ва уларни соғлом бўлиб вояга етказишлари тўғрисида қомусий олимларнинг фикрлари ҳақида батафсил маълумот берилган.

Калит сўзлар: мусиқа, маданият, санъат, ғоя, ижод, эстетик, тарбия, восита, ўқувчимактаб, қизиқиш.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о мнениях восточных мыслителей о важности воспитания художественно-эстетических ценностей, привития лучших человеческих качеств в сознании студентов и молодежи через музыку и доведения их до взрослой жизни здоровым путем.

Ключевые слова: музыка, культура, искусство, идея, творчество, эстетика, образование, инструмент, школа, интерес.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 “ On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom”, of May 30, 2019 “On the organization of the activities of the state museumreserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD6000 of May 23 [3].

From time immemorial, the great thinkers of the East have used artistic aesthetic values as an important means of education. The foundations of Eastern

spirituality are expressed in the works of Imam al-Bukhari, Imam al-Termizi, Abu Nasir Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Yusuf Khos Khajib, Alisher Navai. At the same time, the role of examples of folk art in providing spiritual-aesthetic and ideological-political education to young people is incomparable. National values have a special place in the development of society. The fact that our national musical heritage has come down to us over the centuries is that the respect for it is a product of a positive attitude.

At this point, Abu Nasr Farabi's thoughts about music deserve attention. Abu Nasr Farabi calls music an educational science and says about its importance: "This science is useful in the sense that it educates those whose character is out of balance, perfects those who are not perfect, and maintains the balance of those who are not in balance. It is also beneficial for the health of the body, because when the body is sick, the spirit withers, and when the body suffers, the soul also suffers. Therefore, the treatment of the body is carried out through the treatment of the soul, under the influence of the voices, the spiritual forces adapt to their substance and come to order and balance".[4]

Abu Ali Ibn Sina's thoughts about instilling the best human qualities in the minds of students and young people through music and bringing them to adulthood are worthy of attention. He classifies sciences in his work "Donishnoma" and shows the ways of learning science in stages. The most important way to achieve knowledge is to bring children under the influence of education from a young age. Therefore, Ibn Sina says that the child should be given to the teacher from the age of six, education should be given gradually, and the child should not be tied to the book all of a sudden. These recommendations of Ibn Sina can be a factor that guarantees the pedagogical effectiveness of learning the art of music today in music circles outside the classroom, not only as a source of musical education and upbringing, but also as a means of understanding the national spirit, that is, the national idea.

The general secondary education system, including the "Music culture" classes, occupies a great place in the spiritual life of our future youth. The following words of Zakhiriddin Mukhammad Babur are noteworthy: "Nobody like Khoja Abdulla Marvori would have followed the Ahl Nagmadin law, because he was disgraced. Another slave was Muhammad Udi, and he used to love the girl, and he wore these three hairs on the girl. Ahl Nagmadin and Ahl Sozdin do not have so many special ties. Peshravdin is not very good at other things. And it was Shaykhi Noyi, he played the oud and the dulcimer as well". [5]

Alisher Navoi says that it is possible to develop students to perfection in all aspects through education. If the student-youth is not influenced by education from a young age, he can fall into the path even in his youth:

After the birth, it was the Shabab, the light of Hira fell and the darkness was filled.

A person's state at this time is twofold, the strength of his mind or his soul
If the mind is dead, good things will happen, sori rahnamun.

There are opportunities for them to implement these teachings and ideas in the process of musical education and upbringing of music clubs outside the classroom. It is appropriate to use these opportunities effectively. [6] The inclusion of examples of our national musical heritage in the curriculum of "Musical culture" will not fail to have an impact on the spiritual, aesthetic and ideological education of the students. Acquainting students with folk art, national values, traditions and rituals, inculcating them in their minds is one of the main tasks of today's musician pedagogues.

Among the factors influencing the education of young generation students, the educational opportunities of extracurricular musical clubs deserve special attention. The issue of improvement of the ideas of the national mentality to this activity is considered as a pedagogical tool, it allows to determine the possibilities of education, the main directions and characteristics, and to reveal the qualities of influence on the personality of the student-youth. Among the many factors of education in leading the young generation to maturity, music clubs have a special place. Here, as the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, stated, "... today, the art of music has a greater and stronger influence than other forms of art in the development of the high spiritual spirit of our modern generation".[7]

Indeed, music with its unique nature has the power to greatly influence the spiritual world of students. After all, under the influence of melody and melody, the growth of the world of emotions, the formation of perception and thinking, the pursuit of goodness, the love of beauty and the preservation of nature. The desire to serve for the development of the motherland is increasing. Musical education and training through music circles is one of the main and complex aspects of the world of sophistication, teaches to perceive and appreciate the beauty around. A person gets acquainted with music through his mother and enjoys it throughout his life. Therefore, the formation of musical culture in students is the main goal of music education.

Today, it is important to educate students and young people in the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland based on the concepts of the national musical spirit. In fact, it is of particular importance to prepare school-age students to actively participate in the development of our country, to form in them the ideas of the development of the Motherland, peace of the country, people's well-being, the perfect person, inter-national harmony, and inter-religious tolerance.

During the years of independence of Uzbekistan, the factors that play an important role in the development of a person, such as the national idea, spirituality, enlightenment, morals and refinement, were expressed in a number of documents of our state. Scientific, philosophical and literary definitions were given to these concepts. In particular, it is known to the general public that an idea is a product of human thinking, and a national idea is a product of national thinking. The national idea is a set of thoughts that gives meaning to the life of a person and society and leads it to a noble goal.

Ideology is a system of ideas that embodies the needs, goals, interests, dreams and aspirations of a certain social group, social stratum, nation, state, people and society, as well as the principles of their implementation. The national idea, which has been passed down from ancestors to generations, has been cherished for centuries, has taken deep root in the hearts of every person and the entire people living in this country, has become their spiritual need and life requirement, so to speak, the most noble dream and aspiration of any nation. If we imagine hope-goals, I think that we will have expressed the essence of such a broad concept.

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